

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ADEDOKUN****FIRST NAME: OLUWASANMI****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.*The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:*The author did use Zotero to insert references.The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

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QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. The following cannot be considered plagiarism and does not need to be referenced.

- None of the above.**¹
- A direct quote from a widely read newspaper.
- An idea from an online video completely rephrased in your own words.
- Data from a manuscript that you had previously published.

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2. The following words are synonymous Standard British English and Standard American English words, except?

- Foreman – Mason.**²

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. (Bangui, Euclid University, 2021), 34.

² Ibid, 26.

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Maths - Math.

Rise - Raise.

Jail - Gaol.

3. A qualitative research genre which involves studying a small number of subjects through extensive and prolonged engagement to develop patterns and relationships of meaning is _____?

Phenomenology.³

Ethnographic study.

Grounded theory.

Critical genre.

4. Which of the following is not a measure of trustworthiness in a qualitative research design?

Repeatability.⁴

Confirmability.

Transferability.

Dependability.

5. Which of the following is the correct rendering of the name of a selected country in a WHO document meant for an external audience?

³ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 35.

⁴ Ibid, 472–79.

Cote d'Ivoire.⁵

Tanzania.

Comoros.

Kosovo.

6. Which of the following is the correct representation of the Nigerian currency in a WHO document meant for an external audience?

₦ 2 140 317.⁶

2,140,317 naira.

NGN 2 140 317.

NGN 2,140,317.

7. Which of the following is not a secondary source of evidence?

Census.⁷

Meta-analysis.

Textbook.

Dictionary.

8. Which of the following is not a component of a scientific argument?

⁵ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide*, Second Edition (Copenhagen: WHO Regional Office for Europe, 2013), 14.

⁶ *Ibid*, 17.

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (University of Chicago Press, 2018), 36.

Proposal.⁸

Evidence.

Claim.

Warrant.

9. Which of the following is the correct plural form of the compound word “Sister-in-law”?

Sisters-in-law.⁹

Sister-in-law’s.

Sister-in-laws.

Sister’s-in-law.

10. When an author introduces words or phrases into a direct quote to make the sentence clearer, the introduced words should be enclosed in _____?

Brackets.¹⁰

Parentheses.

Curly brackets.

Double quotation mark.

⁸ Ibid, 56–67.

⁹ Ibid, 303.

¹⁰ Ibid, 324.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.